

Inner Line Permit and Scheduled Tribe Status Demands in Manipur

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Abstract: In recent years, identity consciousness among the people of Northeast India, especially in Manipur, has grown significantly. Key factors include the concept of single citizenship and the ongoing migration into the region. After Manipur attained full statehood in 1972, concerns over migrants and outsiders sparked several movements. The demand for the Inner Line Permit (ILP) system and Scheduled Tribe (ST) status for the Meitei community are central to these efforts. Since January 1, 2020, Manipur became the fourth northeastern state to implement the ILP. The paper explores the socio-economic and political factors driving these identity-based movements in Manipur.

Keywords: ILP (Inner Line Permit), Indigenous People, Scheduled Tribe Status and Meitei/Meetei.

Introduction:

Identity consciousness is a global phenomenon that often manifests in the form of identity politics. According to Cressida J. Heyes, "Identity politics typically concerns the liberation of a specific constituency marginalized within its larger context." Movements such as the civil rights movement, LGBTQ+ liberation, anti-racism campaigns, and ethnic-based movements are key examples. In India, the idea of unity in diversity is a cornerstone of democracy. North East India, sharing borders with Bangladesh, Myanmar, China, Bhutan, and Nepal, holds strategic importance. The porous borders contribute to a steady influx of migrants seeking social, economic, and educational opportunities. Manipur, located in this region, is home to various ethnic communities. The Meiteis, indigenous to the area since 33 A.D., have long coexisted with other groups such as the Tangkhul, Kabui, Maring, Mao, Anal, and Clothe each with distinct identities and self-governing systems. During British rule (1891–1947), these groups were categorized under broader labels such as Naga and Kuki and later granted Scheduled Tribe status. Today, the Scheduled Tribe population forms about 35.12% of the state's total (2011 Census). With rising migration and resource pressure, the Meitei community seeks constitutional protection to preserve their identity, land rights, and cultural heritage.

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Ethnicity As Viewed Under the Indian Constitution

Northeast India is home to a rich tapestry of ethnic groups, each with its own language, culture, and identity. However, from an outsider's perspective, the entire region is often viewed as a single unit, overlooking its diversity. The region is characterized by its multi-lingual, multi-religious, and multi-cultural composition. Over time, this diversity has given rise to various ethnic-based political aspirations, identity politics, and at times, conflicts. While this paper does not delve into ethnic conflicts, it is important to understand the roots of identity consciousness in the region.

During British colonial rule, administrative policies such as land alienation and the introduction of a new land revenue system facilitated the influx of outsiders who later settled permanently in the region. This period marked the beginning of identity consciousness among indigenous communities, largely driven by economic concerns and the need for social survival. After independence, however, these demands evolved to become more political in nature.

The 1971 Bangladesh Liberation War triggered another wave of migration into the region, especially affecting states like Tripura, where the indigenous Tripuri population became a minority. Assam witnessed a major anti-foreigner movement from 1979 to 1985, demanding the deportation of migrants who entered after 1951. Manipur too has seen several movements, including calls for the implementation of the Inner Line Permit system and the demand for Scheduled Tribe (ST) status for the Meitei/Meetei community.

Ethnicity, by nature, is complex, and every community possesses layered identities. While the Indian Constitution protects religious and linguistic minorities under Articles 29 and 30, it does not define "minority" based on ethnicity. As per the National Commission for Minorities Act (1992), only six religious groups are recognized as minorities. The Meitei, although not officially recognized, inhabit less than 10% of Manipur's geographical area and lack constitutional land protection. As the sole custodians of a unique and ancient culture, the Meitei deserve recognition as an ethnic minority in India.

Definition Of Indigenous Population in The Context of Meitei People

Across the world, indigenous peoples have long sought recognition for their identity, traditional way of life, and rights over ancestral lands and natural resources. While international organizations such as the United Nations, the International Labour Organization (ILO), and the World Bank recognize the concept of "Indigenous Peoples," there is no universally accepted definition. However, common markers include self-identification as a distinct ethnic group, shared ancestry, a deep-rooted connection to land, and a

common language and culture (United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2014, p.34). Terms like tribal people, aboriginals, or first nations are often used interchangeably with indigenous peoples.

In India, the Constitution does not explicitly use the term “Indigenous Peoples.” Instead, it refers to “Scheduled Tribes,” a term developed post-independence. Yet, by international standards especially those set by the UN and ILO the Meitei community of Manipur aligns with the criteria of an indigenous group. The Meitei have a long and documented history dating back to 33 A.D., as recorded in *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the royal chronicle of Manipur. Over 74 kings ruled the land until 1955, shaping a rich cultural and political legacy.

Despite undergoing significant changes, especially during the early 18th century Hinduization under King Pamheiba, Meitei society has retained many unique traditions. Rituals surrounding birth, marriage, and death are still practiced, and the community continues to believe in its divine pantheon and traditional customs. As Sanajaoba (1988) explains, tradition is not static; it is a dynamic process, continuously interpreted by each generation.

Today, the Meitei community maintains a distinct cultural identity rooted in centuries of history, values, and practices. In this context, the Meitei can be regarded as an indigenous group, deserving recognition and protection of their unique heritage and rights.

Movement For Inner Line Permit System and Land Distribution System in Manipur

Manipur, a small state nestled in Northeast India, was once an independent kingdom with its own sovereign administration. Ruled by its kings, the state operated through traditional institutions and community-based customary laws. Migrants or outsiders were strictly regulated. While a few did settle in the region, they typically assimilated into local society without conflict. There was no notable anti-outsider movement during the monarchy because the traditional governance structure balanced local customs with external influences.

This harmony changed after the Anglo-Manipur War of 1891, when the British annexed the state. The hill areas came under direct British administration, while the plains were governed indirectly through a puppet ruler. For administrative convenience, the British created a clear divide between the hill tribes and the valley people. They introduced land revenue systems that served colonial economic interests and allowed

controlled migration. A "Foreign Department" was established to monitor and regulate the entry of non-Manipuris.

A major shift occurred after Manipur merged with the Indian Union in 1949. The dissolution of the Foreign Department led to unregulated migration. Migrants began arriving from across India and neighboring countries like Myanmar, Bangladesh, and Nepal. The Indo-Nepal Treaty of Peace and Friendship (1950) further enabled unrestricted migration between the two countries, which significantly affected the demographic composition of Northeast India, including Manipur.

The rising influx of migrants posed a serious threat to indigenous communities, especially the Meiteis, in terms of land ownership, employment, and cultural preservation. Before Manipur became a full-fledged state in 1972, many top administrative, legislative, and judicial positions were held by non-Manipuris. This imbalance gave outsiders undue influence and encouraged more migration into the region.

By the 1980s, anti-outsider sentiments intensified, inspired in part by the anti-foreigner movement in neighboring Assam. In Manipur, local student organizations such as the All-Manipur Students' Union (AMSU) and the All-Manipur Students Coordinating Committee (AMSCOC) led mass protests. They called for the identification and deportation of illegal migrants and pushed the central government to act. A memorandum of understanding was eventually signed with the Government of India, recognizing the urgency of the issue.

This period also saw heightened public awareness. Insurgent groups like the People's Revolutionary Party of Kangleipak (PREPAK) and the Kangleipak Communist Party (KCP) supported the anti-outsider movement, often invoking pan-Mongoloid identity and ethnic pride. Cultural expressions such as banning Hindi films and reviving the traditional Meitei script, Meitei Mayek, reflected a broader desire for cultural preservation and autonomy.

When government responses remained inadequate, a second wave of protests erupted in 1994. The focus shifted to the rapid settlement of migrants in Imphal and other parts of the state. These new settlers, many of whom did not integrate with local communities, were perceived as a threat to the indigenous way of life, particularly that of the Meiteis.

Amid these concerns, the demand for the Inner Line Permit (ILP) system gained momentum. Originally introduced by the British under the Bengal Eastern Frontier Regulation Act of 1873, the ILP is a travel

document required by Indian citizens to enter certain protected areas. It also restricts non-locals from purchasing land in these areas.

Unlike neighboring states such as Arunachal Pradesh, Mizoram, and Nagaland, Manipur did not have ILP protections. In response, civil society and student groups organized mass movements, and in 2012, the Committee on Inner Line Permit was formed. The Joint Committee on Inner Line Permit System, Kangleipak (JCILPS), cited alarming statistics—such as claims that 71% of voters in the Jiribam subdivision were migrants. In 2015, the Manipur Assembly passed the Protection of Manipur People Bill to regulate the entry and stay of non-locals and preserve the indigenous identity.

The bill defined a "Manipuri" as someone whose family name appeared in the National Register of Citizens (1951), the Census Report of 1951, or the Village Directory of that year, including their descendants. This demand gained urgency with the introduction of the Citizenship Amendment Bill (CAB), which excluded ILP-protected areas from its jurisdiction. Protesters feared that without ILP, CAB would provide legal status to illegal immigrants in Manipur. One student lost his life during the protests. Ultimately, on January 1, 2020, the ILP system was extended to Manipur, making it the fourth northeastern state to come under its protection. However, activists continue to push for more effective guidelines and implementation.

Land rights have become another pressing concern. After independence, all land was legally placed under government ownership, with constitutional protections for Scheduled Tribe (ST) communities. Articles 19(d) and 19(e) of the Indian Constitution provide freedom of movement and residence, but also allow for reasonable restrictions to protect tribal interests. Non-tribals are barred from purchasing land in tribal areas a rule reinforced by the Manipur Land Revenue and Land Reforms Act, 1960.

However, this Act does not apply to the hill areas of Manipur, where tribal communities reside. Section 158 of the Act restricts land transfers by Scheduled Tribes to non-tribals without prior permission. The valley, home to the Meitei population, is not covered by these protections. Since Meiteis are not classified as Scheduled Tribes, their lands are open for purchase by outsiders, leaving them increasingly vulnerable to land alienation.

This issue is further complicated by India's federal structure. Land is a State subject under the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution. Article 371C provides special administrative provisions for Manipur's hill areas. Still, tribal customary laws prevail in these regions. Among the Kukis, village chiefs hold control over all land, while the Nagas follow more democratic systems. Meiteis, however, have no similar legal or customary protection.

Over time, the Meitei population has declined in relative numbers. In 1951, Meiteis made up 59% of Manipur's population. By 2011, this had fallen to 44%. Other indigenous groups in Manipur benefit from dual protections as Scheduled Tribes and as religious or linguistic minorities. Despite their rich history and cultural legacy, Meiteis remain without such safeguards.

In response, the Meitei community has actively demanded Scheduled Tribe status. The Scheduled Tribe Demand Committee of Manipur submitted memoranda to both the central and state governments, arguing that the Meitei/Meetei people have lived in Manipur since time immemorial. They were listed as a tribe in earlier records, including the 1931 Census. However, when the official list of Scheduled Tribes was notified under Article 342(1) of the Constitution in 1950, the Meiteis were excluded.

This exclusion has left the community without constitutional protection, making them more vulnerable to the pressures of migration, land loss, and cultural erosion. The demand for Scheduled Tribe status is not merely a political aspiration; it is a call for survival, justice, and the preservation of a unique cultural identity deeply rooted in the land of Manipur.

The Committee claim that:

- The indigenous Meitei/Meetei who are original inhabitants of Manipur since time immemorial were recognised as one of the tribes of Manipur in successive government records including that of 1931 census.
- But the indigenous Meitei/Meetei community was indiscriminately left out of the Scheduled Tribes prepared under Article 342(1) of the Indian Constitution in 1950 on an indisputably inauthentic and unjustifiable basis. Since then, the community has been victimised without any constitutionally safeguards to date. As a result, the Meitei/Meetei have been gradually marginalised in their ancestral land i.e. Manipur. Their population which was 59% of the total population of Manipur in 1951 has now been reduced to 44% as per 2011 census.

The Following List of Points Is Intended to Promote Uniformity Among All Indigenous People.

1. The Indian Constitution permits positive discrimination to uplift marginalized groups and achieve real equality.
2. Regular review of reservation and minority provisions is essential to ensure fairness and relevance over time.

3. These provisions should be implemented uniformly—either extended to all indigenous groups or adjusted to reflect equal treatment.
4. Ensuring equal status for every indigenous group in Manipur can help reduce ethnic tensions and promote social harmony.
5. Both central and state governments must take proactive steps toward inclusive and balanced development.

Conclusion:

Single citizenship and demographic imbalance have been some of the factors for identity crisis among the indigenous inhabitants of Manipur. Various demands have been put forward for Constitutional safeguards of the indigenous people in the state like ILP (Inner Line Permit) system and Scheduled Tribe Status. The demands made by the indigenous people to safeguard their indigenous right are considered lawful and acceptable under international law. The States all over the world are expected to act in compliance with the international law. Adequate constitutional safeguards will ensure protection of the future of indigenous people like Meitei/ Meetei.

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